

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND UV-VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA OF LEAD(IV) COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						Absorption maxima	
			Pb	C	H	N	S	I	λ_{max} kK	ϵ_{max} $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
PbPh ₂ (ptu) ₂ I ₂	220-21	9.72	22.26 (22.55)	34.06 (33.95)	2.65 (2.83)	6.15 (6.09)	6.64 (6.97)	28.62 (28.50)	37.84 22.22	10740 1463
PbPh ₂ (o-totu) ₂ I ₂	270-72	10.12	21.65 (21.89)	35.06 (35.47)	2.92 (3.17)	5.64 (5.92)	6.83 (6.76)	26.92 (27.23)	38.58 21.98	16560 1598
PbPh ₂ (o-MeO.ptu) ₂ I ₂	230-32	12.25	21.38 (21.15)	34.62 (34.31)	2.84 (3.06)	5.63 (5.72)	6.48 (6.53)	26.21 (26.33)	37.03 22.22	15950 1633
PbPh ₂ (HO.ptu) ₂ I ₂	225-26	10.47	21.56 (21.79)	32.56 (32.80)	2.86 (2.73)	5.68 (5.89)	6.52 (6.73)	26.94 (27.11)	37.58 22.22	11040 1760
PbPh ₂ (dptu) ₂ I ₂	157-58	7.62	19.42 (19.35)	41.83 (42.58)	3.28 (3.17)	5.18 (5.23)	5.62 (5.97)	23.82 (24.07)	35.58 22.22	5082 267
PbPh ₂ (entu) ₂ I ₂	143-45	9.16	25.19 (25.36)	26.24 (26.43)	2.47 (2.69)	6.71 (6.82)	7.62 (7.83)	31.23 (31.56)	37.03 21.98	25000 2854
PbPh ₂ (o-phentu) ₂ I ₂	166-68	9.95	22.38 (22.65)	33.83 (34.10)	2.63 (2.40)	6.45 (6.12)	6.64 (6.95)	27.98 (28.18)	34.36 22.32	6310 632

sulphur bonding^{11,12}. A medium-strong band in the region 290-270 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibration. The metal iodine stretching frequency was not observed as it absorbs below 200 cm^{-1} .

The electronic spectra of ligands and their complexes were studied in 1,4-dioxane solution and absorption maxima observed in case of complexes are presented in Table 1. The ultraviolet spectra of the ligands exhibit intense absorption maxima at 40-37 kK (ϵ 16000-8000) and a less intense band around 34 kK (ϵ 6000-1000). The higher energy band is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition while lower energy band is assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of thiocarbonyl group of the ligand molecule. These transitions are very well compared with the thiocarbonyl $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at 254 nm and thiocarbonyl $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at 291 nm of the thiourea molecule in diethylether. In complexes these transitions were not shifted to appreciable extent but only broad and more intense band is observed in the range 37-34 kK (ϵ 25000-5000). A new band is observed around 22 kK (ϵ 3000-250) in all the complexes. This band may be due to the ligand metal charge transfer which clearly implies that a stable complex has been formed.

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Study of Pseudo Aromatic Behaviour and Stereochemistry of 4-(Ethyl)imino-pentane-2-one Complexes of IV Main Group Elements

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CONSIDERABLE work has been reported on the aromatic behaviour of coordinatively saturated, neutral and monomeric metal acetylacetonates¹⁻³. These complexes form molecular complexes by the donation of electron density from the chelate ring to the iodine molecule. However, no attempt seems to have been made to extend these studies to similar complexes of Schiff bases. With this in view, the dielectric and refractometric techniques have been employed for determining the formation and stoichiometry of the molecular complexes of metal Schiff base derivatives with iodine. From the experimental data, the geometry of the resulting complexes has also been inferred.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were dried by the usual methods^{3,4}.

Stock solutions of metal complexes and ligand were prepared in carbon tetrachloride and the solutions employed for the measurement of dipole moments were freshly prepared from the stock solutions. The dipole moments were calculated by the following three methods⁵.

(i) Higasi's method :

$$\mu^2 = \frac{27KTM_s(a_0 - a_\infty)}{Nd_1(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2}$$

(ii) Guggenheim's method :

$$\mu^2 = \frac{9KT}{4\pi N} \frac{3}{(\epsilon_1 + 2)(\eta^2 + 2)} \frac{\Delta}{W}$$

(iii) Dielectric-refractive index method :

$$\mu = 0.0128 \sqrt{(P_T - P_D)T}$$

$$P_T = \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} \frac{M}{d}$$

$$P_D = \frac{\eta^2 - 1}{\eta^2 + 2} \frac{M}{d}$$

where all the symbols have their known meanings⁵.

The refractive index (η) was measured with the help of a refractometer at room temperature under sodium lamp. The dielectric constants (ϵ) was determined with the help of a standard graph plotted for the various non-polar solvents of known dielectric constants.

The refraction cm^3 of solvent (ϕ_0), acceptor (ϕ_A) and solution (ϕ) have been calculated by the following relations.

$$\phi_0 = (\eta_0^2 - 1) \frac{M}{(\eta_0^2 + 2)}; \phi_A = (\eta_A^2 - 1) \frac{M}{(\eta_A^2 + 2)}, \text{ and}$$

$$\phi = (\eta^2 - 1) \frac{M}{(\eta^2 + 2)},$$

where η_0 , η_A and η are the refractive indices of solvent, acceptor and solution (donor+acceptor), respectively. The difference in refraction/ cm^3 of solution and solvent is given by $10^3(\phi - \phi_0) = 6000(\eta - \eta_0)\eta_0 / (\eta_0^2 + 2)^2 = \delta\phi$.

The ligand was synthesised by the usual condensation method of acetylacetone with ethylamine in unimolar ratio in benzene medium.

The metal derivatives were prepared by mixing diorganometal dihalide with the sodium salt of the ligand in 1 : 2 (M : L) molar ratio in benzene. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate was dried under reduced pressure after being washed repeatedly with dry hexane. It was then analysed for the metal and nitrogen contents.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the resulting molecular complexes has been determined by using the dielectric and refractometric titration techniques^{6,7}. In the dielectric titration technique, the change in dielectric constants (ΔE) of a solution of one component (iodine) on addition of successive amounts of the other component (metal complex) is measured, whereas in the refractometric technique, the difference in refraction/ cm^3 ($\delta\phi$) of solution and solvent is measured with respect to change in the

concentration of the donor. When the polar donor is added to a non-polar acceptor, a complex is formed, which has a larger dipole moment value than that of the donor. The addition of a small amount of donor produces an equivalent amount of the complex. The dielectric constant (ϵ) and refraction/ cm^3 (ϕ) show an increase with the successive additions of the donor and continue to do so until equivalent quantities of the donor and acceptor are present.

Fig. 1.

The Figs. 1 and 2 clearly indicate this increase in ΔE and $\delta\phi$ and also a break at the equal donor-acceptor molar ratio showing the formation of 1 : 1 molecular complexes under the conditions of equilibrium,

On further addition of the donor solution, the dielectric constant increases by an amount depending on the dipole moment of the donor itself.

Fig. 2.

According to Zubieta and Zuckerman⁸, the organic group tends to assume a *cis*-configuration in the octahedral arrangement of the six-coordinated complex, if this is stereochemically feasible. In case, the donor atoms themselves hold the organic substituents, the systems tend to adopt a *trans*-configuration to minimize the ligand-ligand interaction.

The dimethyl tin-bis-acetylacetonate⁹ has been reported to have a *trans*-configuration, whereas

similar diphenyl¹⁰ derivative shown to have a *cis*-structure. In the present case also, the higher values of dipole moment (5.8μ) as well as the spectral studies of the diphenyl lead bis-Schiff base derivatives indicate that the two phenyl groups are present at the *cis*-position, whereas the dialkyl metal bis-Schiff base derivatives (Table 1) have a *trans*-structure as indicated below.

where, $M = \text{Si, Ge, Sn or Pb}$; $R = \text{Me, Et or Bu}$.

As all the above derivatives have the same symmetry (octahedral structure)⁹⁻¹¹ almost similar values of dipole moments are expected. However, the role of the metal ion cannot be completely ruled out and slight variations in the dipole moments can be explained on the basis of the differences in the electronegativities of the respective elements and the possible role of $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding in the chelates.

The dipole moments of the molecular complexes of iodine with Me_2SiL_2 , Bu_2GeL_2 , Bu_2SnL_2 , Et_2PbL_2 , as well as the ligand (L) were calculated by the same procedure and the data are enlisted in Table 1. An increase in the dipole moment values has been noted on complexation with iodine and on this basis it can be concluded that the resulting molecular complexes with iodine are of charge-transfer type.

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENT VALUES (μ) OF SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES AND THE CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR COMPLEXES WITH IODINE

Sl. no.	R	M	μ values (Debye)	
			R_2ML_2	$R_2ML_2 \cdot I_2$
1.	Me	Si	0.745	1.075
2.	Bu	Ge	0.822	1.142
3.	Bu	Sn	0.885	1.159
4.	Et	Pb	0.924	1.174

In the infrared spectra the ν_{C-N} vibrations ($\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the R_2ML_2) remain unaltered in the corresponding molecular complexes of iodine ($R_2ML_2 \cdot I_2$), showing thereby the non-involvement of azomethine nitrogen; the only probability for the formation of these complexes is the donation of electron density through the ring of the acetylacetonone to the iodine molecule and thus providing an additional support to the pseudo-aromatic character of these chelate rings.

The electronic spectra of ligands exhibit three bands around 250, 315 and 400 nm. The bands around 250 and 315 nm are possibly due to $\pi-\pi^*$

transitions of benzenoid ring in conjugation with double band of azomethine group¹², and the band around 400 nm may be due to the $n-\pi^*$ transition¹³ of bonding electrons present on the nitrogen of the azomethine group. In the corresponding aluminium complexes, there is no shift in the position of the first two bands. The ligand band around 400 nm shows bathochromic shifts of 20 nm in the complexes and this may be due to the coordination of nitrogens of azomethine groups to the central aluminium atom. However, in the case of molecular complexes of iodine there is no shift in the position of this band, which further confirms the above observations of ir spectra that in the molecular complexes of iodine, the azomethine nitrogens do not take part in coordination.

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Aquo-bis(diethyldithiocarbamato)nitrosyl Chromium(I)

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AFTER the isolation of potassium salt of nitrosyl-pentacyanochromate(I)¹, several other cationic complexes of hexacoordinated chromium(I)^{2,3} have been reported. However, only a few neutral complexes of nitrosyl Cr^I have been characterised^{4,5}. We report the isolation and characterisation of a new hexacoordinated complex of monovalent chromium containing diethyldithiocarbamate as ligand.